

Novel approaches for design and evaluation of cost-effective surveillance across the food chain (NOVA)

1st plenary meeting

Rome (Italy)
28 February – 1 March 2018

Venue:

Globus Hotel (28 February 2018)
Viale Ippocrate, 119

Istituto Superiore di Sanità (1 March 2018)
Aula Bovet - Via Castro Laurenziano, 10
Via Giano della Bella, 34

REGISTRATION FORM

**To be returned by email to Gaia Scavia (gaia.scavia@iss.it) before
19 February 2018**

Dear Colleague,

This form is intended to confirm your participation in the 1st Annual Meeting of the NOVA project.

Accommodation and airplane tickets and costs will be booked and covered **by your Institute**.

Participant's name:	
Name of the Institute/laboratory:	
Phone no:	Email:
WPs group discussion (please tick one of the box to indicate the discussion group you're joining on 1 March):	
<input type="checkbox"/> WP1 – Food chain surveillance mapping	
<input type="checkbox"/> WP2 – Analysis of food purchase data	
<input type="checkbox"/> WP3 – Syndromic surveillance	

WP3 – Spatial risk mapping

WP5 – Evaluation of surveillance programs & cost efficiency

A light lunch will be available before the start of the meeting 28 February 2018. We hope that everyone wants to join for dinner in the evening the same day. A catered lunch will also be served 1 March.

Food Allergies: No Yes

Please specify: _____

Vegetarian: No Yes

Vegan: No Yes

Other requirements: _____

Would you like to join the **dinner** on **28 February**?

Yes No

Suggested hotels close to ISS:

- Globus Best Western (<http://www.globushotel.com/>)
- Hotel delle Province (<http://www.hoteldelleprovince.it/>)
- Hotel Mercure (<http://www.mercure.com/it/hotel-3304-mercure-roma-piazza-bologna/index.shtml>)

General Map of the area (blue circle: suggested hotels; red star venue of the meeting)

